

A functionality taxonomy for document search engines

Rik D.T. Janssen

Ordina Institute
Groningenweg 6
2803 PV Gouda
The Netherlands
Rik.Janssen@ordina.institute.nl

Henderik A. Proper*

Ordina Institute
Groningenweg 6
2803 PV Gouda
The Netherlands
E.Proper@acm.org

PUBLISHED AS:

R.D.T. Janssen and H.A. Proper. A functionality taxonomy for document search engines. White paper, Ordina Institute, Gouda, The Netherlands, EU, June 2001.

Abstract

In this paper a functionality taxonomy for document search engines is proposed. It can be used to assess the features of a search engine, to position search engines relative to each other, or to select which search engine ‘fits’ a certain situation. One is able to identify areas for improvement. During development, we were guided by the viewpoint of the user. We use the word ‘search engine’ in the broadest sense possible, including library and web based (meta) search engines.

The taxonomy distinguishes seven functionality areas: an indexing service, user profiling, query composition, query execution, result presentation, result refinement, and history keeping. Each of these relates and provides services to other functionality areas. It can be extended whenever necessary.

To illustrate the validity of our taxonomy, it has been used for comparing various document search engines existing today (ACM Digital Library, PiCarta, Copernic, AltaVista, Google, and GuideBeam). It appears that the functionality aspects covered by our taxonomy can be used for describing these search engines.

Keywords: document search engine, document query engine, taxonomy, document retrieval.

1 Introduction

Searching almost forms an integral part of our life. This paper focuses on automated searching. Due to the omnipresence of computers, search engines can be found in almost any application area, as stand-alone or integrated in other packages, and in a variety of settings. They can be used for very different tasks, ranging from simple fact finding to more complex decision making and research tasks.

Examples of stand-alone document search engines are found on the web. Their number and capabilities have increased considerably over the past few years, mainly caused by the expansion of the Internet. There, search is considered to be one of the most visible and important activities [Bre01]. However, the web is not the only place where stand-alone document search engines can be found. Other examples are Digital Libraries and databases from large libraries. One may even consider a (human) librarian to be a special type of ‘search engine’.

Document search engines integrated in other packages can be found in e.g. Document Management Systems and in Workflow Management Systems. There, one may imagine a search engine using role or task bound profiles as a tool for helping workers to find the right information. This variety of search engines leads us to define document search engines in this paper in the broadest sense possible.

The structure of this paper is as follows. In the remainder of this section we discuss how we started with this research and what we consider to be a document. Section 2 provides a theoretical perspective on search

*Also: University of Nijmegen, Sub-faculty of Informatics, Information Retrieval and Information Systems Group, Toernooiveld 1, 6525 ED Nijmegen, The Netherlands,

engines, where the focus is on the functionality as it may be observed by a searcher. This is followed, in section 3, by the current version of our functionality taxonomy. Before the conclusion, in section 4 we use this taxonomy to position some existing search engines. We have taken six search engines to illustrate how they compare to each other.

1.1 How we started

Given the currently existing variety of search engines and their ways of deployment, a natural question to ask is ‘what functionality may be offered by a search engine?’. This was the starting point for the development of the functionality taxonomy as presented in this paper.

Our functionality taxonomy focuses on functionality rather than on the order in which the functionality is actually provided by a search engine. Thus, the focus is on *function* rather than on *process*, which acknowledges the fact that two search engines may cover the same kind of functionality, but use a different process flow (strategy) to help users satisfying their information need. Also, it may be very well possible that the same search engine (as a service to the user) offers different ways for combining functionality.

The taxonomy as presented here, is a first iteration of ongoing research, where we both considered theoretical models for functionality of search engines as well as operational search engines. Examples of its use are:

- to gather, develop or select guidelines on what functionality is useful (and to what extent) for applying a search engine in a given situation;
- to determine the (practical and theoretical) possibilities of search engines;
- to determine if a given search engine ‘fits’ some intended purpose;
- to position different existing (components of) search engines with regard to their functionalities and strategies;
- to develop standards, based on clearly demarcated areas of functionality, for the development of open and standardized search infrastructures.

On some of these points, the taxonomy does need further refinements. Also, quantifications are required for some of the areas of functionality to measure the extent and quality to which a given search engine provides that functionality.

1.2 Documents — that what we seek

The actual information that is sought by searchers who turn to a search engine is likely to be stored in some *document collection*. We (just as the organizers of DocEng 2001 [SDE01]) hold to an expansive notion of documents: a *document* is a representation of information that is designed to be read or played back by a person. It may be presented on paper, on a screen, or played through a speaker and its underlying representation may be in any form and include data from any medium. A document may be stored in final presentation form or it may be generated on-the-fly, undergoing substantial transformations in this process. It can include extensive hyperlinks and form part of a large web of information. Furthermore, apparently independent documents may be composed, so that a web of information may itself be considered a document.

Examples of such documents include: photographs, maps, radio fragments, movies, a snapshot of the web, and any combinations thereof, such as documents containing images and video fragments in any format.

2 A searcher’s perspective on search engines

We have focused our efforts on functionality that may be directly observed by users, independent of the search actor (role). This is done on purpose, since a functionality in the taxonomy may be performed by more than one actor where each has its own strengths: for example, searching can be done by the user (the expert considering the information need, knowing the best what needs to be retrieved), by a librarian (who is the expert in information retrieval, having access to resources others have no access to, or are not aware of) or by an automated search engine (which may be more easily accessible than a librarian).

Figure 1: The information disclosure paradigm.

In figure 1, a conceptual architecture of a document information system and its context is given. An author delivers content to a document base, possibly characterized using some method. If desired, feedback can be obtained. On the other side, a searcher expresses an information need to a search engine, which returns the relevant documents. We call this the *information disclosure paradigm*. It is inspired by the information discovery paradigm [PB99] with the addition of the author’s perspective.

For clarity, we make a clear distinction between search engine functionality, supporting the disclosure of information, and functionality supporting storage of information. In this paper, we focus on the left half of figure 1: the searcher and the search engine. It is quite likely that a ‘commercial-off-the-shelf’ document information system offers both document storage and search engine functionality in one single software package.

From a searcher’s perspective, the information disclosure paradigm highlights some of the key challenges confronting search engines. Whenever humans have an information need, they try to formulate a query with the aim of obtaining an answer that best satisfies their need. This may sound trivial, but there are several caveats. To mention a few: formulating a query is not so straightforward, some places may be more appropriate than others to go for the information (but which ones?), and finding the ‘right’ information between all sources returned in an automated search procedure is not easy. Thus, the initial query will usually only be a crude description of the actual documents needed to fulfill the information need. Therefore, further refinements are done as the search proceeds. This process is usually called *relevance feedback* [Rij79].

The need for information can be caused by a number of reasons. Usually, this is due to some perceived ‘gap’ in the searcher’s knowledge. A gap that may range from being fairly specific such as an answer to the question ‘when did Mahatma Gandhi die?’, to very broad, such as learning about ‘the world of Mahatma Gandhi’. A specific need can usually be satisfied by a small collection of facts, while a broad need usually requires a wider variety of facts. During the search process users may learn more and more about their knowledge gap, and may thus discover aspects of this gap they were initially not aware of. This means that the actual information need of a user may evolve as they are exposed to new information.

Traditionally, the quality of a search engine is measured in terms of precision and recall [Rij79]. These only measure the ability of a search engine to effectively execute a query. This seems less suitable for assessing interactive systems, because in many interactive settings, users require only a few relevant documents and do not care about high recall [LO98, BDM00]. Useful other metrics to define successful queries include: time required to learn how to use the system, time required to achieve goals on benchmark tasks, or the error rate.

3 Functionality taxonomy

Functionality of search engines can be distinguished at different levels of detail. In the initial version of our taxonomy, we distinguish seven general functionality areas, represented by rectangles in figure 2. These seven functionality areas to fulfill information needs are: an indexing service, user profiling, query composition, query execution, result presentation, result refinement, and history keeping. Each of these

Figure 2: The functionality taxonomy. A tree-like representation has been used to emphasize functionality rather than a particular order.

functionality areas relates and provides services to other functionality areas. In subsequent versions of the taxonomy, more detailed levels of functionality and quantifications thereof will be added.

The general functionality areas user profiling, query composition, and result presentation, have been further subdivided into different aspects. These aspects are intended to fully cover the functionality area directly above it. For example, for the user profiling functionality area, we consider the three aspects interface preferences, domain knowledge, and cognitive mode. In subsequent versions of the taxonomy, additional aspects are likely to be identified.

The remaining functionality areas have not been subdivided yet; not because these are not considered to be important, but rather since we have decided to focus initially on functionality directly observed by a searcher. These areas are briefly discussed in section 3.4.

3.1 User profiling

User-interface design for information retrieval tasks is a non trivial task with its own set of challenges, such as diversity of the user communities broadly accessible resources like the web or library systems propose to serve [SBB97]. The successfulness of the search is influenced by the variety in (cultural and professional) background, experience, and knowledge. It is therefore that for search engines user profiling is an important functionality.

Currently, we distinguish three aspects which together comprise a user profile:

- interface preferences,
- domain knowledge, and
- cognitive mode.

These aspects are explained in more detail below. The user profile is concerned with the way in which a searcher wants to use a search engine, both for the long term (some user preferences) and for the short term (some cognitive modes), both dynamically (domain knowledge which changes due to queries and their results) and more-or-less statically (some user preferences). Ideally, user profiles should be portable between search engines, so that searchers can use different search engines more easily.

3.1.1 Interface preferences

Interface preferences are concerned with the style of user interfacing that is to be used. This can depend on many things, such as the preferences or the information need of the searcher. Possibilities include command language, form fill-in, selection from a menu, and natural language.

Depending on the user interface, there are several ways to interact with the searcher. For instance, the searcher might prefer the keyboard, or rather use a pen-pad to sketch a shape he wants the search engine to retrieve. Other possibilities are speech input and output, or files to interface with a statistical software package.

Searchers with differing levels of experience may be supported by appropriate variations in the user interface. There are two variants of experience between searchers: differences in experience of the searcher with the search engine (both frequency of use and the skill of the searcher with a particular search engine) and differences in domain knowledge of the searcher (see the next section). It can be argued [HS99] that both influence the effectiveness of the search. An example of adapting the user interface to the skill of the searcher with a particular search engine is given in [Sch92]:

- first-time searchers need an overview to understand the range of services plus buttons to select actions;
- intermittent searchers need an orderly structure, familiar landmarks, reversibility, and safety during exploration;
- frequent searchers demand shortcuts or macros to speed repeated tasks and extensive services to satisfy their varied needs.

3.1.2 Domain knowledge

Searchers with different domain knowledge need different answers to their queries. For instance, a searcher wanting to learn a new computer language who is a novice in the area of computer programming, needs an introductory text and a gentle introduction to the computer language itself, while someone who is already able to program in several different computer languages may only need a reference book.

Adapting search engines to searchers with varying degrees of domain knowledge is a more difficult task than adapting search engines to the experience of the searcher with that particular search engine, since in the former case there has to be a way for the system to ‘learn’ the level of expertise from the searcher. This is dynamic knowledge, since the domain knowledge of a searcher is likely to change while reading the answers returned from a query.

3.1.3 Cognitive mode

Searchers may be in various cognitive modes when they turn to a search engine [PB99, PW01]. One may think of examples such as able to learn or not, happy or not, in a hurry or not, tired or not, or willing to try something new or rather use somewhat more familiar. Not many (if any) search engines existing today are sensitive to a searcher’s cognitive mode.

Automatically detecting a searcher’s cognitive mode is not an easy thing to do. Using contextual information such as the time of the day or the task at hand, may help in resolving this mode [RL94]. Knowing it may allow a search engine to better tune its activities to the searcher, and subsequently, to improve the satisfaction of the searcher. Besides, it also determines the way results should be presented to the searcher. Another example aspect of a cognitive mode is the overall search goal, i.e. is the goal to obtain an answer:

- to a precise question (one answer exists and can be given) such as ‘When did Mahatma Gandhi die?’.
- to fill a gap in the searchers knowledge (many answers are possible, maybe there is no definite answer), such as ‘What were the circumstances in which Mahatma Gandhi died?’
- to learn about a certain subject on the basis of a ‘recommended concise reading list’, such as ‘Tell me about the world of Mahatma Gandhi’.

Each of these search goals is more complex than its predecessor and requires more functionality from the search engine.

3.2 Query composition

The query composition functionality assists searchers in formulating their information needs in terms of a query. We distinguish three aspects which form the query composition functionality (to be discussed in the following sections):

- collection selection,

- formulation support, and
- strategy selection.

It can be observed that existing search engines have a wide diversity in user-interface, query language, etc., and that no ‘standard’ exists (yet) to prevent inconsistencies between different search services. Also, often the processing of the search engine on the input of the searcher and how the search engine executes the query is unclear.

This is important, since some searchers may use more than one search engine, and by unclarity what exactly happens after they have entered their query, lower performance, uncertainty, mistaken assumptions, and failures to find relevant documents, may occur. This is illustrated by the following example (from [SBB97]), where the search string ‘Hall effect’ could produce (among many other possibilities) a:

- search on the exact string ‘Hall effect’;
- case-insensitive search on the string ‘hall effect’;
- probabilistic search for ‘Hall’ and ‘effect’;
- probabilistic search for ‘Hall’ and ‘effect’, with higher weights if ‘Hall’ and ‘effect’ are in close proximity;
- error message indicating missing AND/OR or other operators/delimiters;
- Boolean search on ‘Hall’ AND ‘effect’;
- Boolean search on ‘Hall’ OR ‘effect’.

In the following sections, the aspects from the query composition functionality are discussed.

3.2.1 Collection selection

Collection selection allows the searcher to choose which collections to use with the current search engine. This makes the user aware of the different collections available. An option is to offer some predefined set.

On the web, queries can be sent to many search engines. Libraries may have several different collections (or databases) with each its own search engine. For example, Pica [PIC01], a company in the Netherlands, offers database services such as NCC (the Dutch central library catalogue) and OLC (On Line Contents)¹. Another service, called PiCarta (see section 4.2) to search these and others databases at the same time, is offered additionally.

3.2.2 Formulation support

Formulation support helps searchers to formulate their query. One of the aspects is that searchers need a clue to decide how to start the query process. Studies show that searchers tend to start out with very short queries, inspect the results, and then modify those queries in an incremental feedback cycle [Ani94]. According to [BYRN99], four main types of starting points for queries can be distinguished.

- Lists: a query is started with a long list of collection names and the searcher is required to guess which one is of interest. From these kinds of lists, frequent searchers may make their own list of ‘favorites’ or ‘bookmarks’.
- Overviews: a searcher can use an overview to select or eliminate the topic domains represented in the various collections. Such an overview can be used to get started, directing searchers to general neighborhoods, after which they can navigate using more detailed descriptions. This starting point is different from lists in that it may offer grouped overviews. One may consider various types of overviews: *category hierarchies*, often associated with a certain discipline such as MEDLINE or ACM, automatically derived by unsupervised *clustering techniques* on the text of the documents attempting to extract overall characterizing themes, and derived using *co-citation analysis* on connections or links between the different documents of a collection. Other possibilities are graphical depictions of bookshelves or piles of books.
- Examples: the searcher is shown a general query template which can be modified to construct a description of what they want. Next, the system shows an example of the kind of information available that matches the description. This may be called *retrieval by reformulation*. Other possibilities are *wizards*,

¹NCC contains bibliographic references and the locations of approximately 14 million books and almost 500,000 periodicals in more than 400 libraries in the Netherlands. OLC contains references to all articles that appear in almost 15,000 current periodicals in all fields of science.

which provide the searcher a step-by-step shortcut through the (usual) sequences of menu choices possible, and a *guided tour*, leading a searcher through a sequence of navigational choices through hypertext links, presenting the nodes in a logical order.

- Automated collection selection: this requires both eliciting the information need from searchers and understanding which needs can be satisfied by which collections. Another possibility is to create a representation of the contents of information collections and match this representation against the query specification, or to send the query to multiple collections and combining the results from the various systems (often used by web-based meta search engines).

Queries can relate to all fields of the database, or to just a few ones. On basis of experience, the searcher may choose to query on certain fields. For instance, when a searcher wants to query for journal articles written by a certain author, he may choose to only access the author-field and not the editor-field to prevent erroneous matches.

3.2.3 Strategy selection

The search engine may apply several strategies when executing a query. In the following paragraphs we discuss some strategies we have encountered while investigating literature and search engines existing today.

Matching options. There are several different ways to match a query to the characterization of a document. Two of the best known are best-match and exact-match (Boolean) search. In addition, several variations of fuzzy-matching and partial-matching² exist.

The study in [BP00] has shown that most common searchers seem to have a preference for best-match systems, while expert searchers seem to prefer exact-match by an overwhelming margin. This seemed to be the case since it is easier to explain searchers why a Boolean system did or did not retrieve a given document, regardless of its actual relevance. This cannot be said for a best-match system. For example, with the query ‘Monarch AND butterfly’, a Boolean system will retrieve all documents that use both words and no other documents, and it will therefore be obvious why any given document was or was not retrieved. When this is compared to the query ‘Monarch butterfly’ for a best-match system, it may be that not only the system likely is to retrieve documents that discuss either queens and kings, or butterflies in general, without mentioning Monarch butterflies; but —worse— it may even be possible that some of these documents rank above any document that really does refer to Monarch butterflies.

Query transformations. There are many kinds of transformations a search engine may apply on a query after the searcher has entered the query. Examples of common transformations are:

- stemming of words, that is dealing with the conversion of words to their presumed roots, e.g. ‘blacker’, ‘blackest’, and ‘blacks’ may all be converted to ‘black’;
- case insensitivity;
- removal of stop words, whereby the system automatically ignores words that are assumed to be so common as to carry little information useful for distinguishing relevant documents from non-relevant ones;
- soundex expressions, where the system also queries for words which sound like the one specified in the query;
- associating weights to query words depending on the position in the query;
- coreference resolution, where the system uses variations in a phrase to refer to an object [Ogi00]. One type is the use of pronouns to refer to a named-entity, for instance, if ‘Mahatma Gandhi’ is mentioned in some query, the object may later be referred to as ‘he’ in the same query.

These kinds of transformations may confuse searchers if systems do not give indication which are being applied. Note that these kinds of transformations may also be applied when deriving characterizations (such as keywords) from documents.

Coreference transformation is a challenging task [Gri97] as it requires some degree of natural language parsing. It can be done on one document in isolation or across documents. There are several types of

²For example, with partial-matching searching for ‘biology’ also retrieves ‘sociobiology’ and ‘astrobiology’.

coreferences, such as the use of pronouns mentioned before. Another type consists of variations on named-entities or noun runs. That means that ‘Mahatma Gandhi’ is referred to as ‘Mr. Gandhi’, or that phrases such as ‘the pacifist’ or ‘the person committed to poor people’ are used. Acronyms are another type.

Multiplicity of queries. Querying a system only one time is different from asking the same query at different time intervals. In the latter case, the searcher probably wants to be kept informed about developments in a certain area or wants to be informed whenever new documents on the same subject are being added to the information collection.

Time of execution. A searcher may want to submit a query to be executed at a later time for various reasons, such as that the time expected for completion may be too long, or that queries at night may be less expensive (i.e. cost less money) to execute.

3.3 Result presentation

The result presentation functionality determines the way the results are displayed. There are two aspects:

- what to present (e.g. which parts and which fields), and
- how to present.

For the latter, results can be presented using visualization techniques or they can be clustered. The use of clustering is based on the cluster hypothesis of information retrieval: ‘closely associated documents tend to be relevant to the same requests’ [Rij79, LA00b]. It appears that searchers are most often confused by not being given any clue in which order the results are presented. Options are, for example, to specify layout and sequencing (alphabetically, chronologically, relevance ranked, etc.). Instead of presenting the searcher an ordered list with results, results can be presented visually (an area wide open to research). Numerous studies suggest that techniques such as topic-based grouping of similar documents (‘how do the resulting documents relate to each other’) are a better way of organizing the retrieval results. An overview of related work on clustering and document visualization can be found in e.g. [BYRN99, LA00a].

3.4 Remaining functionality areas

This section briefly discusses the remaining functionality areas as mentioned in figure 2. In future reports these will be subdivided in several aspects and discussed in more detail. In the section 4 the taxonomy from this section will be used to assess selected search engines.

3.4.1 Indexing services

Indexing services offer indexes on the documents in the document collections. These indexes can be generated on the fly or in advance, automatically or by hand. Search engines may generate these themselves or obtain (and possibly combine) them from the various collections and information sources they have access to. Indexing services may also provide access to thesauri.

To generate indexes automatically numerous document recognition and interpretation techniques may be used. As these techniques are outside the scope of this paper, they are not discussed.

3.4.2 Query execution

This functionality is concerned with the actual execution of the query. The basic result set may be post processed to become more useful to the searchers, for example to remove duplicate answers obtained from separate search engines or to remove all but the top-10 answers.

Queries may be activated explicitly or implicitly. Typical is to have searchers click on a ‘search’ button to initiate the search and then wait for the results. Another alternative is that of dynamic queries: the result set is continuously displayed and updated during the query process. This approach most often requires high bandwidth and (for large databases) very rapid processing. Some advantages are that searchers can broaden, narrow, or refocus their query several times in as many seconds.

search engine		ACM DL	PiCarta	Copernic	AltaVista	Google	GuideBeam
indexing service		×	×		×	×	
user profiling	interface preferences				×	×	×
	domain knowledge						
	cognitive mode						
query composition	collection selection		×	×			
	formulation support	×	×	×	×	×	×
	strategy selection	×	×	×			
query execution		×	×		×	×	
result presentation	what to present	×		×	×	×	
	how to present	×	×	×	×	×	
result refinement		×	×	×			
history keeping		×	×	×			

Table 1: The evaluation of search engines according to our taxonomy.

The search engine interprets the query and may respond with some abstract form of the query, allowing the searcher to modify it. As this might be especially useful for the expert searcher, this step may be hidden from the non-expert user.

3.4.3 Result refinement

The searcher may choose to reformulate the query to obtain different or more to the point answers. This is facilitated by the result refinement functionality. Relevance feedback is used to specify, for example, which query results resembled the searcher’s need and which did not. This kind of feedback can be used in a new or modified query to the search engine.

3.4.4 History keeping

History is important when queries are rephrased multiple times and submitted again to the search engine, or when documents returned from the query are explored. The history is useful because the searcher is able to know where he/she was going to and from where he/she came. History keeping can be done with e.g. certain visualization techniques.

4 Search engine evaluation

We evaluated different search engines to assess the ‘effectiveness’ of our taxonomy as well as to obtain an overview of what types of functionality was provided. The following search engines have been evaluated: ACM Digital Library, PiCarta, Copernic, AltaVista, Google, and GuideBeam. In table 1 the overall evaluation results are shown. Some aspects are discussed shortly in the next sections, however, for the direct comparison with the taxonomy one is referred to the table.

For this paper, due to time and space limitations, we have chosen to only use a Boolean scoring approach. A cross in the results table means that the search engine provides some of that functionality. We did not show to what extent this functionality is provided. An empty cell simply means that the functionality is not provided. Depending on one’s search goal, that may be ‘good’ or ‘bad’. As mentioned in the introduction, one of the next steps should be to define, for each area of functionality in the taxonomy, suitable quantifications that allow to quantify to what extent and quality a search engine offers this functionality.

4.1 ACM Digital Library

The ACM Digital Library [ACM01] offers on line access to a vast resource of bibliographic information, citations, and full-text articles. The library offers an indexing service by browsing the ACM journals and magazines and the ACM proceedings by subject, sponsor or series. Formulation support can be obtained

by browsing e.g. the ACM proceedings. One can also specify which terms to use for which fields (title, full text, abstract, review, and index terms), and there is a separate facility for querying on author names.

For the strategy selection there are many possibilities. In formulating the query the usual expressions like AND, OR, NOT, and NEAR can be used or more uncommon ones like fuzzy, synonym, soundex, and stem searches. After the execution of the query (where one can inspect the internal query representation) one has the option to choose what to present (brief and full listings) and how to present (all search results or a limited number). Results can be ordered by score, publication title or publication date.

Results can be refined using the same operators available as the first query. Each query can be saved in what is called a 'personal binder'. If searchers want, they can be notified with email on updated query results.

4.2 PiCarta

PiCarta [PIC01] is a service offered by Pica, and gives (in the basic form) on line access for members to NCC (the Dutch central library catalogue), OLC (On Line Contents), and NetFirst (a catalogue for Internet resources). The searcher can choose which of these collections to query and on which types of material (books, articles, letters, audio visuals, printed music, etc.).

Formulation support is offered for all fields in the database such as the usual author and title fields, but also on several codes and other specialist fields such as ISBN and ISSN number, Library of Congress number, and on accepted medical terms. Query terms can be combined using the usual Boolean operators and using wildcard and proximity operators. Stop words are removed.

PiCarta has only one method for result presentation: all fields in lists of 10 items. This list can be sorted either on relevance or on year of publication. Refinement can be done by combining the results from different queries or by doing a reduce, enlarge or except search on the query results. Query results are saved for one session only.

4.3 Copernic 2001 Pro

Copernic 2001 Pro [Cop01] is a meta search engine for web pages, installed on the computer of the searcher. It offers access to approximately 1000 search engines and 93 specialized search categories.

Formulation support is provided by using the specialized search categories. One can use the usual Boolean operators, and there is support for scheduled search updates. Results can be emailed. There is no query execution since the query is sent to the different web search engines, of which Copernic only combines the results.

Result presentation allows searchers to choose to show all documents or only the new, downloaded, refined or check marked documents. Results can be sorted using title, score, web address, or date found. Refinement of the results can be done by using Boolean operators. Another form of refinement consists of downloading the query results and removing dead links.

4.4 AltaVista

AltaVista [Alt99] is one of the 'oldest' search engines for the web. It uses a keyword based indexing and querying mechanism.

Searchers can specify several preferences, such as the interface language, filtering of adult content and several display preferences. AltaVista allows searchers to focus their searches on a specific website, domain or region, rather than on the whole web. To help searchers in finding their way, AltaVista also offers a topic-based web directory. This directory is of a similar structure as the one provided by the Open Directory Project [ODP01], and seems to be maintained by AltaVista themselves.

4.5 Google

Google [Goo01] is based on a technology called PageRank [BP98]. This technology relies on text-matching techniques as well as on mechanisms to rank the quality of sites. This mechanism is based on the link

structure ‘surrounding’ a page: the more it is referenced, the higher the value (and, probably, the higher the quality).

Searchers can specify several preferences, such as the interface language, filtering of adult content, preferred language for searched documents and display preferences. Google allows searchers to focus their searches on a specific website, rather than on the whole web. To help searchers in finding their way, Google also offers a topic-based web directory, based on the Open Directory Project.

4.6 GuideBeam

GuideBeam [Gui01] is a meta-search engine that focuses on helping searchers to formulate a query. The resulting query is executed using one of three search engines (one of which is Google).

GuideBeam is basically a research prototype that uses a query-by-navigation strategy to aid searchers in formulating their information needs [BBWW98]. The underlying idea is to present searchers with an abstract presentation, in terms of noun-phrases, of the information that is available to them. This allows searchers to clarify their information need in a process where they first specify some keywords to the system. These keywords provide the system clues on the searchers actual information need. Rather than, like most search engines do, immediately returning large result sets, the system continues by returning suggestions on possible refinements of these keywords in terms of more complete noun-phrases. This refinement (and enlargement) process continues until searchers are satisfied with the reformulation of their information need. This result is used to compute the real result set using the selected query engine.

4.7 Search engine evaluation conclusion

The search engines in the sections above were chosen because some give access to large information collections where new documents are only added whenever they fulfill some standard (ACM Digital Library and PiCarta), where others give access to large information collections (the web) where anyone can add new documents (the others).

Copernic and GuideBeam were chosen because both are meta search engines, the first installed on the computer of the user and the latter directly accessible from the web. AltaVista is one of the ‘oldest’ search engines, and Google was chosen because GuideBeam uses it as search engine.

Another reason for choosing these six search engines with very different design goals was to illustrate that the various functionality aspects present in our taxonomy are present in today’s search engines (with the exception of ‘domain knowledge’ and ‘cognitive mode’, which are candidates for further research).

As can be observed from table 1 AltaVista and Google have the same score. This is caused by the Boolean scoring approach. However, some searchers are likely to appreciate one above the other, probably because of the presentation of the results or differences in perceived quality. A scoring mechanism using quantifications could have captured these differences. In a future paper we will present such a scoring approach.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we have proposed a functionality taxonomy for document search engines. This taxonomy emphasized functionality from the viewpoint of the searcher. The word ‘search engine’ in this paper is meant to be used in the broadest sense possible, so that it includes web based (meta) search engines, library search engines, and so on.

The taxonomy distinguishes seven functionality areas: indexing service, user profiling, query composition, query execution, result presentation, result refinement, and history keeping. It has been set-up in a hierarchical way, which means that more detail can be added as needed.

Next, this taxonomy was used for comparing various search engines. We have evaluated several search engines existing today: ACM Digital Library, PiCarta, Copernic, AltaVista, Google, and GuideBeam. It appears that the functionality aspects covered by our taxonomy can indeed be used for describing these search engines. However, further refinement of the taxonomy is needed, as well as the quantifications for measuring the extent (and quality) in which a search engine provides a certain functionality.

The taxonomy in this paper may also be viewed as the starting point of an architecture for an open and standardized search infrastructure. Interesting research areas are e.g. portable user profiles, common development frameworks for search and retrieval engines, and the development of (components of) search engines.

References

- [ACM01] ACM Digital Library, 2001.
<http://www.acm.org/>
- [Alt99] *Altavista search engine project*, 1999.
{<http://www.altavista.com>}
- [Ani94] P.G. Anick. Adapting a full-text information retrieval system to the computer troubleshooting domain. In *Proceedings of the Seventeenth Annual International ACM-SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval*, pages 349–358, Dublin, Ireland, July 1994. ACM Press.
- [BBWW98] F.J.M. Bosman, P.D. Bruza, Th.P. van der Weide, and L.V.M. Weusten. Documentation, cataloging and query by navigation: A practical and sound approach. In C. Nikolaou and C. Stephanidis, editors, *Research and Advanced Technology for Digital Libraries, 2nd European Conference on Digital Libraries '98, ECDL '98*, volume 1513 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 459–478, Heraklion, Crete, Greece, EU, September 1998. Springer Verlag, Berlin, Germany, EU.
- [BDM00] P.D. Bruza, S. Dennis, and R. McArthur. Interactive internet search: keyword directory and query reformulation mechanisms compared. In *Proceedings of the 23rd Annual ACM Conference of Research and Development in Information Retrieval (SIGIR'2000)*. ACM Press, 2000.
- [BP98] Sergey Brin and Lawrence Page. The anatomy of a large-scale hypertextual web search engine. *Computer Networks and ISDN Systems*, 30(1–7):107–117, 1998.
- [BP00] D. Byrd and R. Podorozhny. Adding Boolean-quality control to best-match searching via an improved user interface. Technical Report IR-210, Center for Intelligent Information Retrieval, University of Massachusetts, Amherst, Massachusetts, 2000.
- [Bre01] E.A. Brewer. When everything is searchable. *Communications of the ACM*, 44(3):53–55, March 2001.
- [BYRN99] Ricardo Baeza-Yates and Berthier Ribeiro-Neto. *Modern Information Retrieval*. Addison Wesley, 1999. ISBN: 0-201-39829-X
- [Cop01] Copernic meta-search engine, 2001.
<http://www.copernic.com/>
- [Goo01] Google search engine, 2001.
<http://www.google.com/>
- [Gri97] R. Grishman. Information extraction: techniques and challenges. In M.T. Paziienza, editor, *Information Extraction: A Multidisciplinary Approach to an Emerging Information Technology, International summer school, SCIE-97*, volume 1299 of *Lecture notes in computer science*, pages 10–27. Springer-Verlag, Frascati, Italy, 1997. ISBN 354063438X
- [Gui01] GuideBeam search engine, 2001.
<http://www.guidebeam.com/>
- [HS99] C. Hoelscher and G. Strube. Searching on the web: two types of expertise. In *Proceedings of the 22st Annual International ACM-SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval*, pages 305–306, Berkeley, California, August 1999. ACM Press.
- [LA00a] A. Leuski and J. Allan. Details of Lighthouse. Technical Report IR-212, Center for Intelligent Information Retrieval, University of Massachusetts, Amherst, Massachusetts, 2000.
- [LA00b] A. Leuski and J. Allan. Lighthouse: showing the way to relevant information. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Symposium on Information Visualization 2000*, pages 125–130, Salt Lake City, October 2000. IEEE Computer Society Press.
- [LO98] E. Lagergren and P. Over. Comparing interactive information retrieval systems across sites: the TREC-6 interactive track matrix experiment. In *Proceedings of the 21st Annual International ACM-SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval*, pages 164–172, Melbourne, Australia, August 1998. ACM Press.

- [ODP01] The Open Directory Project, 2001.
<http://www.dmoz.org/>
- [Ogi00] P. Ogilvie. Extracting and using relationships found in text for topic tracking. Senior honors thesis. IR-209, Center for Intelligent Information Retrieval, University of Massachusetts, Amherst, Massachusetts, 2000.
- [PB99] H.A. Proper and P.D. Bruza. What is Information Discovery About? *Journal of the American Society for Information Science*, 50(9):737–750, July 1999.
- [PIC01] Pica library database, 2001.
<http://www.pica.nl>
- [PW01] H.A. Proper and Th.P. van der Weide. Information coverage – incrementally satisfying a searcher’s information need. In C. Stephanides, editor, *Universal Acces in HCI: Towards an Information Society for All*, pages 719–722, New Orleans, Louisiana, USA, August 2001. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Mahwah, New Jersey, USA. ISBN 0805836098
- [Rij79] C.J. van Rijsbergen. *Information Retrieval*. Butterworths, London, United Kingdom, 2nd edition, 1979.
- [RL94] A. Ram and D. Leake. A framework for goal-driven learning. In M. des Jardins and A. Ram, editors, *Proceedings of the 1994 AAAI Spring Symposium on Goal-Driven Learning*, pages 1–11, 1994.
- [SBB97] B. Shneiderman, D. Byrd, and W. Bruce Croft. Clarifying search, a user-interface framework for text searches. *D-Lib Magazine*, January 1997. ISSN 10829873
- [Sch92] B. Schneiderman. *Designing the User Interface: Strategies for Effective Computer Interaction*. Addison-Wesley, Reading, Massachusetts, 2nd edition, 1992.
- [SDE01] ACM Symposium on Document Engineering 2001, call for papers, 2001.
<http://www.documentengineering.org>